

**WEST AFRICAN JOURNAL OF
EDUCATIONAL ADMINISTRATION
AND PLANNING (WAJEAP)**

Print ISSN: 3026-9202

Online ISSN: 3043-4386

Vol. 2, July, 2024

*Special edition of the
Presbyterian University of East Africa, Kenya.*

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EDITORIAL DESK

I wish to express my profound gratitude to Almighty God for the grace to successfully complete the volume 2 of the West African Journal of Educational Administration and Planning (WAJEAP).

The twelve articles were the products of well researched papers that were presented at the international conference held in May 2024 at the Presbyterian University of East Africa in Kikuyu, Nairobi, Kenya. The conference was well attended by over 25 universities across the globe. These published articles have been peer reviewed and plagiarism checks conducted on them before publication.

I, therefore, want to deeply appreciate the management team of the Presbyterian University of East Africa for making this publication a reality. All the writers and authors are congratulated for passing the stringent measures set by the guild of editors.

Congratulations to everyone.

Prof. M. O. B. Mohammed FNAEAP

Head, Editorial Team

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HEALTH EDUCATION AS A TOOL FOR PREVENTING THE SPREAD OF CHICKEN POX AMONG THE RESIDENTS OF AGELETE IBA LOCAL COUNCIL DEVELOPMENT AREA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated Health Education as a tool for preventing the spread of chickenpox among the residents of Agelete, Iba Local Council Development Area. Two research questions and hypotheses were formulated for this study. The survey research design was adopted, and the population of the study comprises all residents of Agelete, Iba local council developmental area. The study comprised 300 students spread across six streets in Agelete, Iba Local Council Development Area in Lagos State, using a multistage sampling technique of simple random and purposive sampling for participant selection. Data collected using a self-developed questionnaire titled "Health Education Tool for Prevention of the Spread of Chickenpox Questionnaire" (HETPCQ). The validity of the instrument was examined by the supervisor and two other experts in the Department of Human Kinetics, Sports, and Health Education. The reliability of the instrument was achieved using the test-retest method. Data collected were correlated using frequency counts and percentages while inferential statistics of Chi-square and regression analysis were used to test the hypotheses of the study at a 0.05 level of significance. The significant value of ($X^2=149.660$, $X^2=120.333$, $F=0.035$, $F=34.749$) was obtained for hypotheses one to four respectively. Findings from this study revealed that there was significant knowledge and practice of healthy living among residents of Agelete, Iba local council developmental area. Further finding revealed that there was a significant relationship between practice and prevention of chickenpox among residents of Agelete, Iba local council developmental area. Health educators and professionals should counsel residents on how they can prevent chickenpox. The Government should provide and implement policies that foster a supportive environment for people with chickenpox.

Keywords: Chickenpox, Health Education, Knowledge, Practice, Prevention.

INTRODUCTION

Over time, a series of diseases have been ravaging the world which has posed a great threat to humanity. These diseases can be communicable and non-communicable. Communicable diseases can constitute significant threats at the local, regional or global level leading to an endemic disease. Communicable diseases are caused by micro-organisms and transferred from one infected person or animal to another person or animal (Soboye, 2017). An endemic is an infection that constantly maintained at a baseline level in a geographical area without external inputs. An example of an endemic is chicken pox. Human is faced with daily challenges of providing for their needs necessary for life sustenance and achievement of life goals (Ogunbamowo & Ashon, 2022). Nigeria's population is 223,804,632 (2.41%) increase in 2022. The population of Nigeria in 2022 was 218,541,212 (2.41%) increase in 2021. (Nigeria Demographic & Health Survey, 2022). Chickenpox is a common childhood and adult disease,

which usually confers lifetime immunity. Varicella (also known as chickenpox) and herpes zoster (HZ, also known as shingles) are caused by varicella-zoster virus (VZV), highly contagious herpes virus (World Health Organization, 2015). The varicella-zoster virus (VZV) causes chickenpox, which is an acute and highly contagious disease that results in blister-like rashes, itching, fatigue and fever (William & Shiel, 2019). The epidemiology of the disease differs between temperate and tropical climates but is common in developing countries where poor sanitation and vaccination are challenges (World Health Organization, 2019). In temperate countries, chickenpox is a disease of children, with most cases occurring during the winter and spring months. The highest prevalence is seen in the 4-10 years-old age group. In the tropics, however, chickenpox disease occurs among adults who are at a higher risk of severe infection. Chickenpox is an airborne disease which spreads easily from one person to the next through the coughs and sneezes of an infected person (CDC, 2015). The incubation period between 10–21 days, after which the characteristic rash appears. It may be spread from one to two days before the rash appears until all lesions have crusted over. It may also spread through contact with the blisters. Those with shingles may spread chickenpox virus to those who are not immune, through contact with the blisters (CDC, 2015). The disease can typically be identified based on the presenting symptom; but, in exceptional circumstances, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) testing of the blister fluid or scabs may be used to confirm the diagnosis (Papadopoulos, 2018). Testing for antibodies may be done to determine an immune person. People usually only get chickenpox once. Even though the virus can be reinfected, these reinfections typically have no symptoms (Breuer, 2015).

In 1954, Thomas Weller used cell culture to isolate varicella-zoster virus from the vesicular fluid of patients with varicella or zoster. A live, attenuated varicella vaccine was developed in Japan in the 1970s. Since its introduction in 1995, the varicella vaccine has resulted in a decrease in the number of cases and complications from the disease. It protects about 70–90 percent of people from disease with a greater benefit for severe disease (CDC, 2015). Routine immunization of children is recommended in many countries (Flatt & Breuer, 2015). Immunization within three days of exposure may improve outcomes in children. Treatment of infected may include calamine lotion to help with itching, keeping the fingernails short to decrease injury from scratching, and the use of paracetamol (acetaminophen) to help with fevers. For those that are at risk of complications, antiviral medication such as acyclovir is recommended (Ogunbamowo, Oladipupo, Ashon & Ligali, 2022).

The African continent is at risk of increased burden of VZV disease; these include the high prevalence of HIV/AIDS, primary infections among the elderly mainly found in tropical countries and diabetes prevalence. These factors overstretch the already challenged healthcare systems in Africa, preventing the management of the complications of many diseases, including VZV. Furthermore, VZV causes varicella and herpes zoster. Most available data on VZV epidemiology from temperate, industrialized countries cannot be used to guide decisions on an immunization policy against VZV in Africa, given Africa's limited resources and healthcare system challenges (Hussey, Abdullahi, Collins, Muloiwa, Hussey & Kagina, 2017).

Varicella-zoster virus is present globally and, where there is no varicella vaccination programme, most people become infected by mid-adulthood. Before the introduction of vaccine, VZV afflicted about 4 million people a year, leading to more than 10,500 hospitalizations, and 100 to 150 deaths. Although the death rate is relatively low (1 in 60,000

cases) it may lead to serious complications, namely, viral and bacterial pneumonia, meningitis, encephalitis, seizures, skin infections and coma (Center for Disease Control, 2019). The mode of transmission of the varicella-zoster virus is from person to person via direct contact with varicella or HZ rash, inhalation of aerosolized droplets from respiratory tract secretions of patients with varicella, or in rare cases from the inhalation of aerosolized droplets from vesicular flu or skin lesions of patients with varicella or disseminated HZ. The virus gains access to the body of the host through the upper respiratory tract or the conjunctiva. Gershon et al., (2017) discovered that after the first infection, the virus lies dormant in the sensory nerve ganglia where it can subsequently reactivate. Comparatively fewer people die from chickenpox worldwide than from other serious infectious diseases such as measles, pertussis, rotavirus, or invasive pneumococcal disease (Gabutti, Bolognesi, Sandri, Florescu & Stefanati, 2019).

Health is a perceived state of complete well-being of an individual and should encompass all dimensions of health with prudent attention given to his morphology and his environment" (Ogunbamowo & Oladipupo, 2021). Health is the constraint in choice from an ailment or injury". Health is a positive multi-dimensional concept involving a variety of features, ranging from ability to integrity, from fitness to well-being. According to this definition, health is an evolving state of mind, body, and relationships perceived by a person, family, group, or community for themselves in a specific time, space, and context (Oleribe, Ukwedeh, Burstow, Gomaa, Sonderup, Cook, Waked, Spearman & Taylor-Robinson, 2018). At present, health education is practically included in all health and strategic programmes carried out at various levels of social life, includes family, school, work, towns and cities, regions, global societies and international communities. Inadequate immunization coverage continues to hamper the health of the children of Africa and remains the cause of millions of preventable deaths. Routine immunizations against Diphtheria, Tetanus, measles, whooping cough, polio and tuberculosis is perhaps one of the most cost-effective interventions for reducing childhood illness and mortality, especially with the addition of other vaccines such as meningitis and yellow fever in endemic and epidemic areas and Tetanus Toxoid (TT) injection for pregnant women. Though immunization has improved since 2003, Nigeria has one of the lowest coverages in the world (Woynarowska, 2017). Immunization is the most beneficial and cost-effective disease prevention. Immunization has expanded and there are development and availability of many new vaccines targeting various age groups and populations and more vaccine-preventable diseases (Ogunbamowo, Oladipupo, Ashon & Ligali, 2022).

Chickenpox infection typically confers immunity for life, however, in rare cases, second attacks of varicella have been documented (WHO, 2014). World Health Organization suggested that countries where chickenpox is an important public health burden, chickenpox vaccination should be introduced into their routine immunization programs (WHO, 2014). Recommended dosing for varicella vaccination may be one or two doses and separated dosing interval. A first dose at 12-18 months followed, if adopted, by a second dose at 4 - 6 years of age is the most common schedule. Otherwise, the second dose can be given to children at an earlier age (below 4 years) provided it is given at least 3 months after the first dose (Marin, 2017). Chickenpox, which is a characteristic vesicular rash is a respiratory infection caused by the varicella-zoster virus, which can be transmitted through airborne droplets and contact with the patient's fresh blisters or mucosal secretions. It is a common acute and highly contagious disease during childhood, and 90% of susceptible children will be infected most of which will not be seeking medical attention. However, complications mainly neurological involvement, which include secondary bacterial infections and severe death were observed

both among cases of children and adults. The risk for disease increases with age but is also elevated in infants and the hypo-immunity. Therefore, this study assesses health education as a tool for preventing the spread of chickenpox in Agelete, Iba local council developmental area of Lagos State.

Research Questions

The following research questions raised for the study:

1. What is the level of health knowledge in the prevention of chickenpox among residents of Agelete, Iba local council developmental area of Lagos State?
2. What health practice promotes healthy living among residents of Agelete, Iba local council developmental area of Lagos State?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were postulated for the study:

1. There is no significant health knowledge of chicken pox prevention among residents of Agelete, Iba local council developmental area of Lagos State.
2. There is no significant practice of healthy living among residents of Agelete, Iba local council developmental area of Lagos State.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive research design adopted for this study and the population for this study consisted of all residents of Agelete, Iba developmental council area of Lagos State. The sample consists of Three hundred (300) residents of Agelete, Iba local council developmental area of Lagos State. Multistage sampling technique was adopted for this study: A simple random sampling technique was used to select six streets (Onikoyi Street, Alhaji Giwa Street, Thompson Ayoyo Street, Emma Street, Iyonu Street, Kola Street) out of twenty streets in the community while Purposive sampling technique was used to select 50 residents per street. The research instrument for this study was a self-developed and validated instruction titled Health Education Tool for Prevention of Chickenpox Questionnaire (HETPCQ) in the Agelete Iba Local Council Development area of Lagos State. The questionnaire divided into two Sections A and B. Section A contained socio-demographic data of participants, while section B contained an opinion question for the participants. The questionnaire adopted a four (4) point Likert modified scale ranging from; Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Strongly Disagree (SD) and Disagree (D). The face and content validity of the questionnaire was ascertained by the experts in the Department of Human Kinetics, Sports and Health Education, Lagos State University, Ojo including the researcher's supervisor. The Test-retest method of reliability was adopted which requires the researcher to administer twenty (20) copies of the validated questionnaire to twenty (20) residents in the Amuwo-Odofin local government area, which is not part of the study, to determine the reliability of the instrument. The calculated Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.81 was obtained. The copies of the questionnaire were personally distributed by the researcher with the help of three trained research assistants to the respondents. Copies of the questionnaires were distributed and collected by the researcher on the spot and data collection lasted for four (4) weeks among residents in the Agelete Iba area of Lagos State. Copies of the administered questionnaire were checked to ensure that they were well completed before leaving the study area. The researcher monitors the process of data collection throughout. Daily review meetings were held at the beginning and end of each day by the researchers and research assistants. Data collected were analyzed using appropriate descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentage for demographic data while inferential statistics of chi-square and regression analysis were used to test all stated

hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The statistical package for social science was used for analyzing the data collected.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1: Frequency and percentage distributions of respondents by Age, Sex, Tribe, Marital status, Religion, and Level of Education.

Age	Frequency	Percentage %
Below 20 years	74	24.7
21-30 years	169	56.3
31-40 years	43	14.3
41-59 years	14	4.7
Total	300	100.0
Sex		
Male	134	44.7
Female	166	55.3
Total	300	100
Tribe		
Yoruba	127	42.3
Igbo	167	55.7
Hausa	6	2.0
Others	0	0
Total	300	100
Marital status		
Married	209	69.7
Single	62	20.7
Widowed	0	0
Separated	29	9.7
Total	300	100.0
Religion		
Christianity	186	62.0
Islam	114	38.0
Others	0	0
Total	300	100.0
Level of Education		
FSLC	27	9.0
O'Level	29	9.7
NCE/Diploma	22	7.3
First Degree	196	65.3
Higher Degree	26	8.7
Total	300	100.0

Table 4.1 Demographic on Age showed that approximately 24.7% of the respondents are within the age bracket of below 20 years, 56.3% were within the age bracket of 21-30 years and 14.3% are within the age bracket of 31-40 years and 4.7% were within 41-59 years.

Consecutively, the demographic on Sex showed that approximately 44.7% of the respondents were male while 55.3% were female. The demographic on Tribe showed that approximately 42.3% of the respondents are Yoruba, 55.7% of the respondents were Igbo, 6.0% of the respondents were Hausa and 0% of the respondents were from other Tribes. The demographic on Marital status showed that approximately 69.7% of the respondents were married, while 20.7% of the respondents were single, 0% were widowed and 9.7% were separated. The demographic on Religion showed that approximately 62.0% of the respondents are Christians, while 38.0% of the respondents practised Islam, and 0% of the respondents practiced other religions. Finally, demographics on Level of education showed that approximately 9.0% of the respondents have FSLC, 9.7% of respondents have O'Level, 7.3% have NCE/Diploma, 65.3% of the respondents have a first degree and 8.7% have higher degrees.

Hypothesis One

Hypothesis one states that there is no significant knowledge of healthy living among residents of Agelete, Iba local council development area of Lagos State. This hypothesis was tested using Chi-square at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in the table below.

Table 4.2: Chi-square (X^2) result on knowledge of healthy living among residents of Agelete, Iba local council development area of Lagos State.

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual	X^2	Sig
Strongly agree	187	100.0	87.0	149.6600.000	
Agree	99	100.0	-1.0		
Disagree	14	100.0	-86.0		
Strongly Disagree	0				
Total	300				

From the result presented in Table 4.2 above, it could be observed that a significant Chi-square value ($X^2=149.660$, $p<0.05$) was obtained at 0.05 level of significance, therefore hypothesis one as stated is hereby rejected. This implies that there was significant knowledge of healthy living among residents of Agelete, Iba local council development area of Lagos State. The distribution of respondents' responses showed that the majority (187) strongly agreed to knowledge of healthy living followed by 99 respondents that agreed, while just 14 respondents disagreed, and no respondent strongly disagreed.

Hypothesis Two

Hypothesis two states that there is no significant practice of healthy living among residents of Agelete, Iba local council development area of Lagos State. This hypothesis was tested using Chi-square at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in the table below.

Table 4.3: Chi-square (X^2) result on Practice of healthy living among residents of Agelete, Iba local council development area of Lagos State.

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual	X^2	Sig
Strongly agree	245	150.0	95.0	120.3330.000	
Agree	55	150.0	-95.0		
Disagree	0				
Strongly Disagree	0				
Total	300				

From the result presented in Table 4.3 above, it could be observed that a significant Chi-square value ($X^2=120.333$, $p<0.05$) was obtained at 0.05 level of significance, therefore hypothesis two

as stated is hereby rejected. This implies that there was significant practice of healthy living among residents of Agelete, Iba local council development area of Lagos State. The distribution of respondents' responses showed that the majority (245) strongly agreed to knowledge of healthy living followed by 55 respondents that agreed, while just 0 respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed.

DISCUSSION

Hypothesis one states that "There is no significant knowledge of healthy living among residents of Agelete, Iba local council development area of Lagos State?" A study was conducted by Yuan, Qian & Huan, (2015) which compared different demographic characteristics, distance from home to the nearest medical institute with health knowledge awareness, and different ways that people receive health knowledge in western China. The health problem of the elderly was at the world's attention, especially the elderly health education issues.

According to the data analysis, rural residents aged over 65 had the lowest level of health knowledge awareness. Due to the lack of ability and knowledge of the elderly with their life behaviour change, they became the type of groups with the most difficulty controlling their health and carrying out healthy education in rural areas. Even though health care for 65-year-olds and above has been listed as an essential public health service, it was not obvious that implementing improvement affects in the progress and rural elderly residents' health problems to be solved. Due to the low education level of rural residents, the health knowledge received channel is relatively single and traditional, the main health knowledge received channels via traditional ways such as doctors (80.45%) and radio, television, newspaper, and magazines (65.78%). Modern channels such as SMS and Internet had the lowest utilization (21.76%). This result coincides with the closer distance from home to the nearest medical institution as the higher score of health knowledge. Due to most residents receiving health knowledge from doctors, the medical institutions were closer to home, the more convenient they went there, and the higher frequency of communication they had. In addition, the dispersion of rural residents living in western rural areas was relatively fewer people in contact with each other, so they received insufficient health knowledge.

In another study by Leung, Marin, Leino, Even and Bialek, (2016), where they obtained information on varicella pre-matriculation requirements in US colleges for undergraduate students during the 2014-2015 academic year. The healthcare professionals and member schools of the American College Health Association (ACHA) were participants in this study. An electronic survey was sent to ACHA members regarding school characteristics and whether schools had policies in place requiring that students show proof of 2 doses of varicella vaccination for school attendance. At the end of the study, only 27% of schools had a varicella pre-matriculation requirement for undergraduate students. Only 68% of schools always enforced this requirement. Private schools, 4-year schools, northeastern schools, those with <5,000 students and schools located in a state with a 2-dose varicella vaccine mandate were significantly more likely to have a varicella pre-matriculation requirement. A small proportion of US colleges have a varicella pre-matriculation requirement for varicella immunity. College vaccination requirements are an important tool for controlling varicella in these settings.

Hypothesis Two states that "There will be no significant practice of healthy living among residents of Agelete, Iba local council development area of Lagos State". A cross-sectional pilot study by Lee, Wilson, Okunowo, Trinh and Sivoravong, (2020) was conducted on

medical residents and fellows who were 57. Surveys collected information on lifestyle behaviours and perceptions of lifestyle counselling and preventive services. Comparisons of study measures were made across residents' specialty and training levels. Fisher's exact and analysis of variance tests were used for statistical analysis. There were several significant differences in perceptions of counselling and screening by specialty and training level. Primary care residents are expected to provide lifestyle counseling and preventive services for patients with chronic diseases; also, physicians' personal lifestyle practice impacts patient care. The purpose of the study was to assess healthy lifestyle behaviours and attitudes to engage in lifestyle counselling and preventive services among residents and fellows in different training levels and specialties. The findings suggested that there are opportunities to improve healthy lifestyle behaviours and perceptions of lifestyle counselling and preventive services among residents in different specialties and training levels. This knowledge can inform the development of training programs in lifestyle and preventive medicine practice during residency and fellowship.

Al-Turab et al., (2018) conducted a study where the study explored the health lifestyles of university students regarding their health responsibility, physical activity, and nutrition. As universities are ideal settings for implementing health promotion programs, planning and implementing those programs to motivate students to be more responsible for their health, engage in regular physical activity, and practice a healthy diet to promote health and prevent diseases are of paramount importance. The findings highlight the need to further investigate the barriers and potential facilitators for a healthy lifestyle in the university environment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that there was significant health knowledge of chicken pox prevention among residents of Agelete, Iba local council developmental area of Lagos State. There was significant practice of healthy living among residents of Agelete, Iba local council developmental area of Lagos State.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the conclusion of this study, it was recommended that:

- Sensitization on the spread of chickenpox and treatment would help to update parent's knowledge on the subject matter.
- Mass media should also be used as a channel for chicken pox among residents.
- A mobile clinic should be established in the community to offer health education information.
- Health educators and professionals should counsel residents on how they can prevent chickenpox.

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